

Black walnut: valuable hardwood tree species

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Black walnut is often grown as a fast-growing tree in intensive plantations

Black walnut (*Juglans nigra* L.) was firstly introduced into parks, gardens and arboretums since 17th century and in forests at the end of the 19th century. This tree species is not very known and used, despite the fact that it is a very promising and multi-purpose tree species. The use of this tree species is really wide and varied. Black walnut wood is sought after and popular for its beautiful color, high strength, durability and it is easy to machine and it resists weather conditions well. The quality of wood surpasses many other fast-growing tree species such as poplars, willows or Paulownia and it is also a suitable tree species for agroforestry systems. Sap in the spring is used to make syrup, which is similar to maple and is used in the food industry. Dried leaves are processed into infusions and teas. The unripe walnuts with the green husks are used in the production of tincture, liqueur, pickled walnuts, soap and extracts used in cosmetics and food industry. Kernels are used as an ingredient in ice creams and other confectionery products. Excellent oil is obtained by pressing the kernels, which is used in the kitchen and in the pharmaceutical industry. Nuts have been used in alternative medicine for a long time and now are presented in various forms as healthy organic products and also as functional foods that have a preventive or supportive functions, thus helping to prevent some diseases. Shells are used for grinding and sandblasting of buildings and metal structures.

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